

Accidental fire due to spray of pesticide in a household

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Abstract : On 13th May 2011 in Pune, India an aerosol insect repellents can exploded in kitchen of a house. The lady processing foods in a gas stove in her kitchen and found some cockroaches near the sink and grabbed a can of insect repellent and sprayed it near the burning gas stove. The flammable aerosol compound propellant came in contact with the flame of the burning stove and it made the explosion. This paper deals the probable causes of the case study and finally some useful general recommendations are discussed.

Keywords : Aerosol, pesticides, flammable, LPG, propellant.

Introduction

Aerosols are increasingly used in household dwellings. Aerosols spray cans are used in many commodities like pesticides, insect killers, hair sprays, deodorants, air fresheners, oven cleaners, tile cleaners, furniture polishes etc. Many people use these products without realizing some of the potential hazards associated with them. In general, it incorporates propellant, in the range of 20% to 95% of the contents and is packed under pressure in the form of liquid. When the nozzle of an aerosol is pressed, the product and propellant are released from the container in the form of a fine mist. Some of aerosol products can be corrosive, flammable or poisonous. Aerosol contains large quantities of propellants often they are flammable, hence hazardous. The LEL and UEL (lower and upper explosive limits) for the common propellants are as shown below (Table 1).

Table 1. The LEL and UEL for the common propellants

Propellant	LEL	UEL
Propane	2.2	9.5
Isobutane	1.8	8.4
n-Butane	1.9	8.5
Dimethyl ether (DME)	3.4	18.0
Dymell 52a	3.9	16.9
134a	Non-flammable	

In general the auto ignition temperatures of the propellant vary from 350 °C for dimethyl ether (DME) to 505 °C for propane, whereas the temperature of an idly burning cigarette is over 540 °C. Boiling points of liquefied gas aerosol propellants varies in the range from -42 °C to +0.6 °C. The vapor pressures of liquefied gas aerosol propellants range from 1.25 atm_g to 7.5 atm_g at room temperature, i.e. 25 °C but as the temperature increases the pressure also increases, i.e. 2.5 atm_g to 12 atm_g at 40 °C. During nozzle pressing the product pressure inside the container can be considerably higher. The common pressure related hazard associated with it is the possible aerosol container rupture. Exposure to liquefied gas aerosol propellants on human can cause severe irritation, redness, tearing, blurred vision and possibility of freeze burn if it comes in contact with eyes and in the case of skin contact there is possibility of severe frostbite depending upon the propellant composition. In general the poisonous symptoms of human health are nervousness, anxiety, tremors and allergic manifestations. Acute symptoms of aerosol exposure include headache, nausea, dizziness, shortness of breath, throat irritation and skin rash and explosion of aerosol products can cause burn and death.

Ames and Crowhurst¹ reported a total of 297 inci-

dents of domestic dwellings in 1982-1984 where LPG is used as propellant. They examined six incidents in detailed, all cases small quantities of LPG used as propellant in the aerosol products. They observed that the LPG released due to overheating and in one case vapour released due to mechanical puncturing. In all cases LPG involved was less than 200 g and the smallest was 30 g. They reported the explosion condition as shown below (Table 2). They also concluded that no attempt was made to correlate the damage caused with the amount of LPG present. They experimentally stimulated these types of incidents where amount of LPG involved less than 500 g and observed that the pressure developed in the range of 14–42 kPa in a domestic room which would cause the severe damage in the room and also injured people. Scerri *et al.*² reported the burns injury for seven people associated with butane cigarette lighter fluid abuse when a group of people sitting within an enclosed space. Yarbrough³ reported that 5% to 45% body surface burn of 18 people in 5 years span affected in the explosion of pressurized aerosol can.

In general aerosol cans contain two different substances, the liquid product which in releasing (the paint, detergent, hairspray, insecticide etc.) and a pressurized gas called a propellant that helps to push the liquid product into the air and turn it into an aerosol cloud. The propellant gas usually turns into a liquid when it's forced inside the can at high pressure during

manufacturing. That makes the propellant and the product mix together. The propellant turns back to a gas when pushing the nozzle and the pressure is released.

Pesticides aerosol can

Pesticide is a general term used to describe a substance or mixture that kills a pest or it prevents or reduces the damage a pest may cause. Pests can be insects, mice or other animals, unwanted plants (weeds), fungi, bacteria or viruses. Pesticides are formulated in liquid, solid and gaseous forms. Pesticides can be classified by target organism, chemical structure, and physical state. In every day normally we used the common categories of pesticides which are insecticides which kills or repel insects, herbicides which kills weeds or unwanted plants, fungicides which kills mould, mildew and other fungi, rodenticides which kills mice and rats, disinfectants kills bacteria, mould and mildew and wood preservatives which protects wood from insects and fungi. Pesticides are often grouped into "families" because they share similar chemical properties, or they act on the pest in the same way. Prominent insecticide families include organochlorines, organophosphates and carbamates. Pesticides also can be classified based upon their biological mechanism function or application method. Most pesticides work by poisoning pests.

Although pesticides are designed to kill pests but some pesticides are harmful for humans. The health

Table 2. Products involved in aerosol explosion conditions (Ames and Crowhurst, 1988)

Incident No.	Product	Can volume (ml)	Estimated LPG content (g)	Cause of leakage of LPG	Ignition source	Category of explosion
1.	Aerosol air freshener	200	30	Overheating by small accidental fire	Fire in radio/cassette	Severe
2.	Aerosol paint spray	400	50	Overheating by gas cooker	Gas cooker	Severe
3.	Aerosol air freshener	300	150	Overheating by electrical fan	Fan heater	Severe
4.	Aerosol air freshener	200	180	Overheating by small accidental fire	Candle flame and small fire	Severe
5.	Aerosol hair spray	440	60	Can punctured with scissors	Gas fire	Moderate
6.	Aerosol air freshener	225	200	Fire	Fire	Severe

Table 3. Some general symptoms from pesticide poisoning

Mild poisoning	Moderate poisoning	Severe poisoning
Irritation of the nose, throat, eyes or skin, headache, dizziness, loss of appetite, thirst, nausea, diarrhea, sweating, weakness or fatigue, restlessness, nervousness, changes in mood, insomnia.	Mild symptoms and vomiting, excessive salivation, coughing, abdominal cramps, blurring of vision, rapid pulse, excessive perspiration, profound weakness, trembling, muscular incoordination, mental confusion.	Mild and moderate symptoms and inability to breathe, extra phlegm or mucous in the airways, small or pinpoint pupils, chemical burns on the skin, increased rate of breathing, loss of reflexes, uncontrollable muscular twitching, unconsciousness death.

effect depends on the type of pesticides and other chemicals that are in the using product. Most often pesticides affect the nervous system and also effects from acute (short-term) exposure or poisonings are shown in following (Table 3). Some spray pesticides are flammable, so used should be carefully. One of the commonly used mosquitoes repellent in India is Hit, Mortein etc. The probable composition of Hit mosquito repellent (Batch No. B-E11109F088) is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Probable composition of insecticides Hit (mosquito repellents)

Composition	Amount (% , w/w)
d-trans Allethrin a.i.	0.25
Synergist (PBO)	0.50
Perfume	0.20
Deodorised kerosene	39.05
Propellant gas (LPG)	60.00
Total	100

The aerosol container is a high-strength metal unit consists of a valve, whose various openings control how much products be comes out, how fast and whether it is a spray, foam or gel, an actuator, on pressing it opens the valve, a dip tube, on pressing the actuator the valve is opened, the product comes up through the dip tube. The can in general a airtight metal container has a designed bottom and top to add strength. An aerosol contain propellant, a compound that exerts pressure and helps dissolve the product as it carries it out of the can. The ingrediants like soap or disinfectants or water that dissolve, dispense, and stabilize the product.

The incident⁴

On 13th May 2011 in Pune, India an aerosol insect repellents can exploded in kitchen of a house. The

lady processing foods in a gas stove in her kitchen found some cockroaches near the sink and grabbed a can of insect repellent and sprayed it near the burning gas stove. There was an explosion and the poor woman was covered in flames, sustaining 65% burns. Her husband tried to rescue her but he was also injured due to the burns and was hospitalized and the house wife was declared dead.

Probable causes

All insect repellents such as Hit, Mortein etc. are most popular in India, have highly volatile inflammable propellant. The propellants are chosen by the manufacturer for the characteristics that they provide for discharge of the base product. Over the past decade the chlorofluorocarbon propellant commonly used in aerosol cans has been replaced with hydrocarbon blends that include propane, butane, and isobutane. At present the propellant is mainly LPG in the aerosol mixture with the active ingredients. In the spray condition the aerosol mist can ignite to form an explosion mixture with oxygen present in air and this explosion can be achieved by only one spark. The house wife used the aerosol insect repellent near the burning gas stove. The flammable aerosol compound propellant came in contact with the flame of the burning stove and it made the explosion. Initially the LPG caught fire and the fire transmitted to the can. The ignite gas inside expands the container ruptures. This gas ignites causing an explosion. This situation is similar as BLEVE (Boiling Liquid Expanding Vapour Explosion).

Recommendations

(1) An aerosol can should be in compliance with international and national safety standards, like Australian Standard AS 2278 (Metal Aerosol Containers),

USA Code Federal Regulations, Title 49 Part 173.306 and Part 178.33 etc.

(2) If there are any changes in the physical property of the can or its contents, i.e. active ingredients or propellants, then retest must be conducted to ensure compliance of the safety norms.

(3) One should comply with the warning labels of aerosol can. Recognized safety standards should be printed in English and local languages. It should include following instructions;

- (i) A warning that the contents include LPG as propellant;
- (ii) Can should not be used near any naked flame;
- (iii) Can should only be used in well ventilated area and should not be directed at any electrical appliances in operation;
- (iv) The can should be kept in safe storage requirements like out of reach of children and well ventilated dry place;
- (v) If it falls on skin then skin should be washed with adequate water and then soap;
- (vi) If eyes are affected, water should be splashed on eyes;

(4) Safe disposal techniques – In general cans are made of steel/aluminium can be recycled. For recycling the can should be completely empty and also the pressure relief valve should be removed.

(5) When using some general aerosol products one

- (i) Should check the aerosol can for damage and leaks;
- (ii) Keep the container in a dry, cool and well ventilated place;
- (iii) Should not make an excessive use of aerosol can;
- (iv) Should not inhale the contents of the aerosol can;
- (v) Should not refill the aerosol can;
- (vi) Should not puncture or burn the used aerosol can;
- (vii) Keep the aerosol can in an enclosed space.

Conclusion

This study reported an accidental case study due to spray of pesticide in kitchen. Due to lack of knowledge the house wife used the aerosol insect repellent near the burning gas stove and the flammable aerosol compound propellant came in contact with the flame of the burning stove and it made the explosion. Finally some useful general recommendations are discussed.

References

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